

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MANIFESTATION OF QUANTITATIVE TRAITS IN F1 AND F2, COMBINATIONAL VALUE OF PARENTAL FORMS AND FORECAST OF THE PROSPECTS OF HYBRID COMBINATIONS

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Abstract

Allelic gene interactions constantly disappear during the process of homozygosity of hybrid populations of self-pollinating plants, and the effects of non-allelic gene interactions can become fixed in individual individuals. In the phenotype of hybrids, there are also effects of gene interactions, as well as many other types, since the number of interactions between polymorphic loci is virtually infinite. However, researchers believe that to some extent it is possible to determine the significance of the effects of gene interactions that disappear during the process of homozygosity of hybrid populations through self-pollination and separate their effects from those that persist. The obtained data on the nature of inheritance of the studied quantitative traits and the combining ability of the parental forms formed the basis for further research on the comparative study of older generations of these hybrids and the determination of the best combinations.

Keywords: homozygosity hybrids, hybrid populations, gens combinations, gens interaction.

According to modern ideas about genes, they are divided into two types: allelic and non-allelic. Allelic gene interactions constantly disappear during the process of homozygosity of hybrid populations of self-pollinating plants, and the effects of non-allelic gene interactions can become fixed in individual individuals. In the phenotype of hybrids, there are also effects of gene interactions, as well as many other types, since the number of interactions between polymorphic loci is virtually infinite. However, researchers believe that to some extent it is possible to determine the significance of the effects of gene interactions that disappear during the process of homozygosity of hybrid populations through self-pollination and separate their effects from those that persist [2].

The method of systematic analysis of the study of quantitative traits by self-pollinating plants is based on the use of the difference in the average values of traits of the first and second generations, which is determined by the effects of gene interaction that disappear during the process of population reproduction and, first of all, allelic ("All."). The effects of other gene interactions that arise as a result of hybridization and are fixed during the transition of hybrid plants to a homozygous state are defined as non-allelic ("non-all.").

Formulas are proposed for determining the effects of non-allelic interactions of genes and, on their basis, the combining ability of the original genotypes and predicting the breeding value of hybrid populations.

As far as we know from the literature, this method was used in the study of quantitative traits of bread wheat; there are practically no such data for the tetraploid group of wheat [1].

Let us trace the nature of inheritance of quantitative traits of ear and plant productivity elements in the first and second generations of 10 hybrid combinations of intra- and interspecific hybrids (2n=28).

Productive bushiness. This trait was inherited mainly by the type of incomplete dominance of the trait of one of the parents or intermediate. True heterosis

was noted only in one combination (turgidum x Sevinj with a level of 4.4%). Our data are consistent with the results of a number of researchers that overdominance is rarely observed for this trait.

The average indicators of this trait in F2 populations were 83.3-106.2% relative to F1. In combinations 2-4, productive tillering was on average 1.6-6.2% higher than F1. Higher average values of this trait in subsequent generations, according to Table 2, were expected in hybrids of the 3rd-5th combinations (FK=106, 1-106.2%). The relative values of non-allelic gene interactions in these combinations are also the largest (9.0-10.3%), which indicates the possibility of positive transgressions. In the combination Kyzyl Bugda x Kharkovskaya 7, overdominance in F2 is due to non-allelic interaction of genes, since in F1 there was intermediate inheritance. For this combination, the non-allelic interaction of genes in relative values is the largest (10.3%). Individual selection involves the selection of hybrid forms with higher productive bushiness than the original genotypes.

Number of spikelets and spike length. In F1, the average ear length for combinations was 6.5-8.9 cm, F2 – 6.7-8.8 cm. Higher indicators of this trait in older generations were expected in the 2nd and 9th combinations (FC = 112 .9-117.0%). The relative indicators of non-allelic gene interactions were greatest in the 2nd and 8th combinations. The Kharkovskaya 7 variety was characterized by high SCS and OCS for this trait.

In terms of the number of spikelets of the main ear, the combinations Novinka 3 x Kharkovskaya 7 and Kharkovskaya 7 x turgidum should be more promising; in terms of relative indicators of "non-allelic gene interactions" - Novinka 3 x Kyzyl Bugda, Novinka 3 x Kharkovskaya 7 and Novinka 3 x Sevinj.

The Kyzyl Bugda variety was characterized by the highest SCS value of this trait, and the Kharkovskaya 7 variety was characterized by the highest SCS value [2].

The number of grains of the main ear. Inheritance of this trait was carried out according to the type

of overdominance and complete and incomplete dominance of the indicator of the best parent. The level of heterosis was 2.2-13.6%. The most grainy ears were the ears of the Turgidum x Sevinj combination. This indicator in the second generation hybrids was on average 1-5 more or less than in F1 (the average number of grains of the main ear of F1 is 45-52, F2 is 43-55). The Kharkovskaya 7 variety and the turgidum form (108 m 122%) were characterized by a high SCS for this trait; Kyzyl Bugda was characterized by a low SCS (94.1%), and the Sevinj variety stood out with a high SCS (16.7%).

The average values of the trait are expected to be high in the older generations of the combinations turgidum x Sevinj, Kharkovskaya 7 x Sevinj and Novinka 3 x Sevinj (FK=133.3; 113.4 and 115.6%). The relative values of non-allelic gene interactions for these combinations are the highest (30, 16.0 and 21%). It was in these combinations that productive lines with a large number of grains per ear were subsequently isolated.

The mass of grains of the main ear. Heterosis for this trait manifested itself in 6 combinations with a level of 4.2-7.2%, complete and incomplete dominance of the trait of the best parent and intermediate inheritance were noted in 4 combinations. Overdominance was observed in F2 of the five combinations. The average of this trait should be higher in the older generations of the combinations Novinka 3 x turgidum, Kyzyl Bugda x Kharkovskaya 7, Kharkovskaya 7 x turgidum and turgidum x Sevinj. More valuable in terms of selection of positive transgressions should be the combinations Novinka 3 x Kyzyl Bugda, Novinka 3 x Kharkovskaya 7, Kyzyl Bugda x Kharkovskaya 7 and Kyzyl Bugda x Turgidum ("non-all." - 12.4-20.5%).

The varieties Kharkovskaya 7 and the form turgidum (121.4 and 122.8) showed high TCS in terms of the weight of grains of the main ear, and high SCS – Kyzyl Bugda. It is interesting that the varieties Kyzyl Bugda and Sevinj are almost equal in terms of SCS, but in terms of SCS they differ greatly: high SCS in the village of Kyzyl Bugda and low in the village of Sevinj.

Weight of grains per plant. Overdominance on this basis in F1 was manifested in 4 combinations. True heterosis was 0.8-18.6% (turgidum x Sevinj and Novinka 3 x Kyzyl Bugda). In 7 combinations, the average values of this trait in F2 were slightly higher (by 1.7-15.3%) than in F1 [3].

Protein content in grain. The protein content in the grain of F1 hybrids was 13.9-16%, F2 – 13.8-17.2% (in parents 13.7-16.1%). In F1, this trait was inherited intermediately or with a bias towards one of the parents (a slight increase in relation to the parents by 0.5% was noted in the combination Novinka 3 x Sevinj and by 0.2% in Kyzyl Bugda x Sevinj). In F2, in most combinations, the average protein content in grain was slightly higher (0.2-1.2%) than in F1. In three combinations it was on average less (0.2-1.5%).

References:

1. Baker R.J., Dyck P.L.-Relation of several quality characteristics to hardness in two spring wheat crosses/ 2000. p.600-925
2. Bhatia et al. Diallel analysis and cross prediction in common bread wheats Austr./ 1999. P.165-187
3. Dewey D.K., Lu K.H. A correlation and path-coefficient analysis of components of crested wheat-grass seed production, 1989,p.511-518